

Competitive Task Offloading in Hierarchical Edge-Cloud Compute Continuum

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Abstract—The introduction of new technologies in user equipment (UE), radio access and the core network has facilitated service provision for task offloading in the recently developed cellular network architectures. One such advancement, has been the shift from classical cloud based designs to a more flexible compute continuum using mobile edge computing (MEC). To serve the requirements generated by novel applications, a redefinition of network interconnections to handle the new traffic considering the inherent challenges is essential. Different works have contributed to the analysis of MEC-based task offloading. The literature manages to capture specific variations of application and system modeling, but in turn, illustrates an absence of a holistic approach on the matter, working as a basis for all other studies. In this work, we propose and evaluate a system for hierarchical task offloading, involving three computational tiers at the Internet of Things (IoT), MEC and the cloud. As the core objective of service deployment, the model includes monetary based metrics to devise offloading policies. Delay-cost trade-off will also be studied. Providing a game-theoretic assessment, the conflicting utility models of each service tier are highlighted, and competitive strategy settings are reported. The outcomes of this work can serve as a benchmark for following inter-tier task offloading mechanisms to be studied, while also stressing the limits of an unregulated system for service delivery, further motivating research directions for orchestrated and incentivized operation.

Index Terms—Hierarchical task offloading, Compute Continuum, Game theory, Monetary based modelling.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of data-driven applications and the increasing demand for real-time processing have significantly reshaped the landscape of modern networking. Internet of Things (IoT) networks are relaying unprecedented volumes of data, leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) analytics to process and extract valuable insights in real time. As a result, AI and its applications are expected to contribute to a 40% increase in research and development (R&D) investment in the telecommunications sector over the next five years [1]. Such emerging use cases stretch the capabilities of traditional architectures, stressing the need for new solutions to enable ubiquitous connectivity and high computational performance for the next generation of applications.

To address the data explosion, networks have been evolving into interconnected federations of processing nodes. Traditionally, resource-intensive demands were processed at centralized cloud servers while delay-stringent tasks were handled at IoT devices; yet centralized cloud architectures, though efficient

in resource pooling, often fail to meet stringent latency requirements for emerging use cases, whereas IoT networks lack the computational power for complex tasks. To address this, edge computing has emerged as a new paradigm, allowing processing tasks to be offloaded closer to the data source. By strategically leveraging execution points across available computing resources in the network to form a compute continuum, edge computing not only bridges the gap between intensive computation and low-latency requirements but also introduces a new level of adaptability and efficiency to network architecture.

Task offloading has been a classical network challenge, gaining a new perspective recently, as in the novel heterogeneous compute continuum, deciding where the tasks will be executed is more challenging [2] [3]. In this context, task offloading has been recently studied in multiple application scenarios. Healthcare, vehicular networks and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) are some prime examples being realised. To make the most of novel network architectures, services are trying to mold into the decentralized and heterogeneous nature of edge computing.

To handle policies in offloading scenarios across the compute continuum, it is crucial to consider the interactions among the different involved stakeholders, such as IoT, edge and cloud providers, network operators, application providers, etc. These multi-stakeholder environments inherently involve conflicting objectives and competition for resources. Among the various tools for modeling and analyzing such systems, game theory stands out for its ability to model interactions among independent entities. Game-theoretic approaches provide a structured methodology to analyze these interactions and derive strategies that balance individual and collective benefits. Furthermore, they enable the exploration of theoretic limits, reducing the complexity of specific models to reveal general principles applicable across diverse scenarios. To further complicate the analysis, business models could be included, giving in return an improved practicality from the stakeholders view. Such approaches have been extensively used in the past to tackle problems such as caching [4] [5] but need a re-evaluation for novel network architectures and applications.

As trends show [6], the introduction of new applications and advanced technologies has recently brought renewed attention to task offloading. Multiple works have tried to capture the

nuances of this diverse problem with different tools, including AI. Each tool has its pros and cons but as practical measures are imposed and parties with conflicting benefits are introduced, game theoretical analysis becomes prevalent. A Stackelberg game approach for roadside processing units was presented in [7], implying the supervision by a centralized controller. Other works present extensive models capturing details on power consumption as in [8] or wireless modeling in [9]. These works provide detailed models but fail to offer a holistic view on task offloading. Therefore, they can not model the ongoing conflict among tiers raised by utility interconnections.

For the literature gaps identified, studies lack an analysis transparent to the infrastructure, network model, and offloaded tasks. Also, competition between tiers has been overlooked, despite affecting many applications and use cases. A study capturing the trade-off between cost and delay is yet to be done.

This paper aims to tackle the aforementioned challenges by focusing on task offloading as a fundamental process within edge computing. Moving beyond economy-based models that emphasize on small scale interactions, we investigate how simplifying assumptions and abstractions can generalize the problem space of hierarchical service provision. By formulating a competitive framework for task offloading, we aim to establish a robust understanding of system behavior under varying system configurations. Our approach highlights the interplay between system efficiency, latency-sensitive requirements, and the operational policies that govern task allocation among distributed hierarchical players. Our contributions can be summarized as:

- Defining a game-theoretic monetary model to fit common hierarchical task offloading scenarios, transparent to offloading details.
- Modeling the competitive interactions with an extensive-form game solution to the framework over pricing and offloading policies.
- Presenting the benchmark of system performance and policies, as well as insights on system management, operational limits and impacts on end user.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

This section reviews the proposed system model. The building blocks are defined and the complete system model is built.

A. Model Building Blocks

The proposed hierarchical model, presented in Fig. 1, is defined as an abstract representation of the compute continuum where tasks could be handled on the IoT devices (IoT), at the Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) servers, and on the cloud.

In the proposed scenario, the end user pays a fee to a service provider (e.g., for a health monitoring application) acting as the sole monetary input to system. The task computation service is then delivered through competition among the three tiers.

Starting from the bottom, the IoT layer is the first tier and is closest to the end user for task handling. Its devices have constrained processing and energy resources. The MEC layer is the second tier and consists of a network of MEC servers, offering more processing power than IoT devices while remaining closer to end users than the cloud. It provides computation services to the IoT layer and charges it accordingly. The cloud is the top tier; it serves tasks not handled by the MEC layer, receives payments from MEC for those tasks, and sets prices for services offered to MEC.

Fig. 1 illustrates a merged model of the three introduced layers, containing the notation for the pricing policies. These three layers form the data plane giving service to the end user.

Fig. 1. Network model and interactions between entities

Each tier incurs an α -weighted latency cost, designed to model the tension between local processing and offloading. This enables us to also study the trade-off between latency and cost. Different studies like [10] [11] have modeled this network property through demand prediction and service probability. In our case, to capture the highly variable processing requirements of the offloaded tasks, we utilize Generalized Pareto Distribution (GPD) to model computation times [12]. In our case, the probability distribution function (PDF) are shown as:

$$f_X(x | \xi, \sigma, \mu) = \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(1 + \xi \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \right)^{-\frac{1}{\xi} - 1} \quad \text{for } \xi \neq 0, x \geq \mu \text{ (and } x \leq \mu - \sigma/\xi \text{ if } \xi < 0)$$
(1)

where x denotes the tasks, and ξ , σ , μ are the distribution variables affecting its start point, tail slope and mean. We will use different constants, referenced in the simulation part to introduce tasks with different computation times to the system. We define the cost for each tier as:

$$C_{IoT}(x) = f_X(x | \xi_{IoT}, \sigma_{IoT}, \mu_{IoT}) \quad (2)$$

$$C_{MEC}(x) = f_X(x | \xi_{MEC}, \sigma_{MEC}, \mu_{MEC}) \quad (3)$$

$$C_{Cloud}(x) = f_X(x | \xi_{Cloud}, \sigma_{Cloud}, \mu_{Cloud}) \quad (4)$$

According to Eq. (2), our proposed model will assign constants for different distributions, modeling computation times of the tasks for each server. Furthermore, to fit the model, the distributions are translated to a tangible cost metric for the system at each tier. We use an α -weighted latency cost, which also allows us to study the effect of task stringency on the policies. The variable α is the leverage to model system loss incurred for different task completion times.

To model price regulation, we consider an inverse relation between price and user preference. We define the user preference, σ , to acts as a leverage to keep the end user satisfied, regulating the monetary interaction between service provider and end user. The preference σ is modeled as a linear relation versus the price paid by the end user, as follows:

$$\sigma = 1 - \rho \times P_{IoT} \quad (5)$$

where P_{IoT} is the subscription price charged to user, and ρ is a constant normalization variable set during the simulation.

Fees paid by end users are the only input to the system, and all other prices are a result of interactions and bargaining between processing tiers. Therefore, taking into account the user preference, all pricing variables have an upper bound constraint, where σ becomes zero and the monetary input to the system is withdrawn. We call these constraints as price constraints and derive them by setting $\sigma = 0$ in eq. 5 :

$$\begin{aligned} P_{IoT} &\leq \frac{1}{\rho} \\ P_{MEC} &\leq P_{IoT} \\ P_{Cloud} &\leq P_{MEC} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

To further develop the model, we differentiate between access rate for different tasks. For that, we use a simple but general form, a discrete uniform distribution with the PDF of:

$$A(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{N} & \text{if } x \in X, \quad |X| = N \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where X is the set of all tasks requested by the end user. This set contains N different tasks with sorted computation times.

Furthermore, to quantify the offloading of tasks, we define the offloading variable $O_{A \rightarrow B}(x)$, setting the amount of tasks offloaded by tier A to tier B for task x . By forming a vector of offloading variables for the same source and destination across all tasks, a server's complete offloading strategy can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{O}_{A \rightarrow B} = [O_{A \rightarrow B}(x_1), O_{A \rightarrow B}(x_2), \dots, O_{A \rightarrow B}(x_N)] \quad (8)$$

To capture the whole system behavior on offloading and convenience of presentation, we also define the following notations:

$$O_{IoT} = \sum_{\forall x} O_{IoT \rightarrow MEC}(x) \quad (9)$$

$$O_{MEC} = \sum_{\forall x} O_{MEC \rightarrow Cloud}(x) \quad (10)$$

where O_{IoT} expresses the number of tasks offloaded from IoT to the MEC, whereas O_{MEC} are the tasks offloaded from the MEC tier to the cloud.

B. Complete Utility Models

The utility of each tier is modeled by putting together all the model components explained in the previous section. As a common property among all tiers, σ affects the whole system's monetary input, and therefore has an impact on each tier separately. Also, the prices are charged and paid as an entire fee by the end user, but each tier can distinguish between the processing costs of various tasks according to their processing complexity and the required resources, and thus retains the corresponding amount. Tasks are demanded according to the distribution in Eq. 7; hence the expected value is calculated over the entire set.

For the cloud, the utility function is given by:

$$U_{Cloud} = \sigma \times \mathbb{E} \left[O_{MEC \rightarrow Cloud}(x) \cdot (P_{Cloud} - \alpha C_{Cloud}(x)) \right] \quad (11)$$

where U_{Cloud} represents the revenue generated by the cloud, and the offloading variable, $O_{MEC \rightarrow Cloud}(x)$ points the amount forwarded to the cloud network from MEC, as defined before. U_{MEC} is the utility function of the MEC tier, and offloading variables follow the previously stated convention:

$$U_{MEC} = \sigma \times \mathbb{E} \left[O_{IoT \rightarrow MEC}(x) \cdot (P_{MEC} - \alpha C_{MEC}(x)) + O_{MEC \rightarrow Cloud}(x) \cdot (P_{MEC} - P_{Cloud}) \right] \quad (12)$$

Finally, the utility function for the IoT is formulated as:

$$U_{IoT} = \sigma \times \mathbb{E} \left[O_{IoT \rightarrow IoT}(x) \cdot (P_{IoT} - \alpha C_{IoT}(x)) + O_{IoT \rightarrow MEC}(x) \cdot (P_{IoT} - P_{MEC}) \right] \quad (13)$$

where U_{IoT} is the utility and $O_{IoT \rightarrow IoT}(x)$ represents the task offloading variable for the ones handled locally at the IoT.

III. FRAMEWORK SOLUTION

As shown in Eqs. (11)-(13), server utilities are heavily interconnected, as any change in one agent's strategy will impact other tiers. This interconnectedness highlights the effectiveness of our analysis for selfish and competitive operation of different network tiers.

Strategic form games model interactions between different players, determining the player's preferred strategy in a single stage. Different players have different bargaining power in the policies. Applying the hierarchical format, more elasticity is added to the model when users take turns in their actions, changing it to an extensive form game.

As the leader-follower game to analyze the non-cooperative operation mode of the three tiers, the cloud is able to control pricing policies before any other party does. On the other hand, since the task is generated closest to the IoT layer, it can choose first whether to serve the task locally or to offload it at the next tier. Following the hierarchy, the MEC tier has control over the system using two different leverages, the price for the service and the number of tasks to be further offloaded to the cloud. Then, the IoT sets the price to be paid by the end user. The sequence of actions is represented as:

- **Step 1:** The cloud sets the pricing, and IoT chooses its offloading policy, determining how many tasks will be offloaded to the MEC.
- **Step 2:** The MEC optimizes policies for both offloading to the cloud and the MEC service pricing.
- **Step 3:** The IoT layer fee is decided.

At each step, the relevant layers utility is maximized, presented in equations (11)-(13). We re-write the utilities using the law of the unconscious statistician, according to the access rate model. We also replace the service preference model from Eq. (5). The problem statement becomes:

$$\max_{P_{IoT}, O_{IoT \rightarrow IoT}(x), O_{IoT \rightarrow MEC}(x)} U_{IoT} \quad (14)$$

s.t. Price constraints, in (6)

$$U_{IoT} = (1 - \rho \times P_{IoT}) \times \sum_{\forall x} A(x) \left(O_{IoT \rightarrow IoT}(x) \cdot (P_{IoT} - \alpha C_{IoT}(x)) + O_{IoT \rightarrow MEC}(x) \cdot (P_{IoT} - P_{MEC}^*) \right) \quad (15)$$

The notation P_{MEC}^* means that when the IoT is trying to optimize its policies, the MEC layer has already set the strategy so it is known to the IoT. The same notation will be used from now on. The next round of action setting is then formed.

$$\max_{P_{MEC}, O_{MEC \rightarrow Cloud}(x)} U_{MEC} \quad (16)$$

s.t. Price constraints, in (6)

$$U_{MEC} = (1 - \rho \times P_{IoT}) \times \sum_{\forall x} A(x) \left(O_{IoT \rightarrow MEC}(x) \cdot (P_{MEC} - \alpha C_{MEC}(x)) + O_{MEC \rightarrow Cloud}(x) \cdot (P_{MEC} - P_{Cloud}^*) \right) \quad (17)$$

And as the last step of the backward induction, cloud sets the policies, without any previous party choosing their actions.

$$\max_{P_{Cloud}} U_{Cloud} \quad (18)$$

s.t. Price constraints, in (6)

$$U_{Cloud} = (1 - \rho \times P_{IoT}) \times \sum_{\forall x} A(x) \left(O_{MEC \rightarrow Cloud}(x) \cdot (P_{Cloud} - \alpha C_{Cloud}(x)) \right) \quad (19)$$

We follow the backward induction solution steps. By expanding the user demand model variable, equations can be simplified. The affinity of values $O_{IoT \rightarrow MEC}(x)$ and $O_{MEC \rightarrow Cloud}(x)$ makes any optimization on equations push this variable to either 1 or 0, affecting eqs. (9) and (10). Considering this point, (14) and (16) are reviewed. Starting from the last step of policy setting, in an interaction between MEC nodes and the IoT, variables $O_{IoT \rightarrow MEC}(x)$ and P_{MEC} are set. In the next game-theoretic step, the MEC server chooses its strategy on offloading, knowing the IoT's resultant action. Then, parts of (14) and (16) related to these policies are solved simultaneously, setting variables $O_{MEC \rightarrow Cloud}(x)$ and P_{Cloud} . At the last step, (14) and (18) are considered, reaching pricing policies for the IoT layer, P_{IoT} .

The final solution to the framework determines the portion of incoming tasks handled by each tier, the workload redirected to higher tiers, and the processing fees charged by each one for the provided services.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In this section, we provide the simulation details, followed by the performance evaluation and analysis of obtained results.

A. Simulation Details

The simulation parameters are summarized in Table I and are further discussed next. Without loss of generality, we consider $N = 100$ tasks generated with an access rate give by Eq. (7). We set the task computation times accordingly, considering CDF of up to 90 percent for each distribution, choosing the values that lead to corresponding probabilities. For this purpose we use quantile function of GPD as described here:

$$Q(p) = \mu + \frac{\sigma}{\xi} \left[(1-p)^{-\xi} - 1 \right], \quad 0 < p < 1, \xi \neq 0. \quad (20)$$

As explained before, the results are reported on a set of different distribution constants, ξ , σ , μ to evaluate the impact

of computation time on the policies. Chosen constants are based on [13] which deploy a practical set up for task offloading and have reported the computation times. These values are reported in Table I. Different α values are chosen for simulation to analyze how policies change when latency requirements are more stringent. Without loosing generality, we set the constant ρ to 0.01 which affects the price constraints in return. A different ρ would lead to a scaling of chosen prices, normalized by upper bound limits which is $P_{IoT} \leq \frac{1}{\rho} = 100$. The other pricing variables are set accordingly. These constants are applied to eq. (6).

TABLE I
SIMULATION CONSTANTS

Constant	Value
N	100
ρ	0.01
σ_1	[12, 48]
σ_2	[22, 88]
σ_3	[140, 480]
μ_1, μ_2, μ_3	0
ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_3	0.25

B. Analysis and Insights

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show the offloading policies taken by each tier, depicting the number of offloaded tasks for different distributions of Pareto in each figure, and different values of the α factor, to show the effect of system loss for more computation time stringent tasks. Distribution of task processing times are reported by steps on the GPD scale factor, as reported in Table I for each layer. The case of $\alpha = 1.5$ models service disruption for discussion purposes.

As a general trend, all parties tend to locally serve tasks with lesser computation times instead of offloading. This emphasizes the necessity of higher processing tiers, such as the MEC and cloud, in service chain to ensure a seamless service provision for computationally intensive tasks.

The MEC policies follow the strategy taken by the IoT tier. This means that when a party with more control decides to change policies, the other tiers get to follow the lead or incur extra loss. This is evident as the IoT sets the lower bound for MEC's offloading choice.

The higher computation times in the distributions, gives an advantage to higher tiers on posing a one-way enforcement of policies. Loosing the bargaining power at lower network tiers highlights the importance of system management, by either designing incentive mechanisms or utilizing the novel network capabilities to reach a more centralized orchestration. A price regulation set by third party entities may also propose a management direction for such challenges.

The plots show that as latency losses increase, tiers get less motivated to participate in computation and offload more. This in return could cause problem for latency stringent computation requests. For example IoT tier is going to serve less tasks

locally as they get more latency stringent, which being counter intellectual, will lead to even worse quality of service for the end user.

Fig. 2. All Task offloading policies for $\alpha = 0.1$

Fig. 3. All Task offloading policies for $\alpha = 1.5$

For the pricing strategies, presented in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, whole system will be operating in line with the cloud network, setting higher prices for more processing intensive tasks. This trend is visible both in each plot when we move to more distributions with bigger mean, also when we shift the α which means the tasks are latency stringent and the system will incur more loss.

Fig. 4. All Pricing policies for $\alpha = 0.1$

Utility plots, are presented in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7. As the tasks to serve become more time consuming, a bigger part of the generated utilities is allocated to just serving the requests, therefore cutting the revenue margin smaller. As the IoT's pricing strategy moves towards the maximum limit, the system tends to generate negligible revenue down to zero. Also as

Fig. 5. All Pricing policies for $\alpha = 1.5$

Fig. 6. System utilities for $\alpha = 0.1$

evident in the break-down scenario for $\alpha = 1.5$, if the system incurs a loss more than the revenue, service provision is halted.

V. CONCLUSION

Our work modeled a holistic case of task offloading, where end user agnostically receives service from a hierarchical processing infrastructure. If not managed by a central decision making unit the inevitable competition between different processing tiers motivated our game-theoretic analysis. The building blocks were combined to form the final utility for each tier. The solution to the extensive-form game of the utilities set the policies for task offloading and service pricing.

Extensive simulations demonstrate that competition, where each tier strives selfishly to gain utility, can harm the service delivered to the end user as ensuring a guarantee is practically impossible. We also include variations of the processing requirements in our model using different GPD factors, which

Fig. 7. System utilities for $\alpha = 1.5$

shows how overall utility starts to decrease as computationally more intensive tasks are introduced to system. Our research sets the benchmark for other works, both in model development and also in operation policies. It serves as a theoretic limit for policies chosen by each tier for such task offloading applications. The huge loss of utility and a restriction in service assurance highlights the necessity for centrally deployed, managed, and monitored offloading frameworks now possible using the novel technologies. Contributing to the ongoing discourse on designing edge computing systems, this study offers a stepping stone toward addressing the management complexities of decentralized networks and achieving optimal performance in such compute continuums.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been supported by the project ELIXIRION (101120135), and by the projects PROXIMITY (PID2021-124122OA-I00/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER, UE).

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